

DEVELOPERS OF CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS

DECISO Digital Ecosystem

User's Guide

Version 2.0

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Introduction

Dear user,
this guide intends to introduce you to the use of the DECISO Digital Ecosystem, the digital support for the DECISO community and its pilots that aims to facilitate the different stakeholders' activities, their information, collaboration and engagement at different levels and scales and to catalyse and organise the convergence of already existing networks, communities, and projects about the Circular Economy within an online socio-technical environment that facilitates and stimulates the direct engagement of the different types of stakeholders identified, facilitating the upscaling of outputs and outcomes.

The Digital Ecosystem is part of the overall exosystemic approach used within the DECISO project, which implies the stakeholders' engagement at different levels and different scales in the face2face, virtual and hybrid activities of the project, but also after the end of the project for exploiting the results and share experiences and the knowledge produced by the consortium.

The tool is directly accessible from the DECISO Digital Ecosystem section of the DECISO project website (<https://www.decisoproject.eu/deciso-ecosystem/index>).

Definitions of notes

We use the following icons throughout this User's Guide:

Technical notes

Alert notification

Technical notes

Use the top menu (1) to navigate within the DECISO Digital Ecosystem, not the browser's back button.

Click on the **Logout** link to leave the DECISO Digital Ecosystem (2).
Click on the **News** link to go to the news section (3).

To register in DECISO Digital Ecosystem, you need:

- a sufficiently stable internet connection;
- your email address or the email address of your organisation.

For a better user experience, please use Chrome 114 or higher.

User registration

If you do not have a DECISO Digital Ecosystem account, click on the menu link **Login** to create your account.

Then, click on the **Register** link to fill in the registration form.

In the first part of the registration form, all fields are mandatory.

REGISTRATION

E-mail (*)

Confirm e-mail (*)

Password (*)

Confirm password (*)

I accept and confirm the [terms and conditions \(*\)](#)

First name (*)

Last name (*)

Country (*) Select an item ▾

Simple user Organization user

[Register](#)

[Back Home](#)

In the second part, the registration form requires some additional specific fields depending on the user type.

In particular, for **Simple user**, the mandatory fields are gender and profile.

Gender (*) Select an item ▾

Profile (*) None selected ▾

Company/Organization

Company/Organization type None selected ▾

Website

Phone

[Register](#)

[Back Home](#)

Instead, for **Organization user** the mandatory fields are website, company/organization and company/organization type.

The image shows a registration form for an organization user. The form includes the following fields and options:

- Website (*)
- Company/Organization (*)
- Company/Organization type (*) with a dropdown menu showing "None selected"
- Phone
- Gender with a dropdown menu showing "Select an item"
- Profile with a dropdown menu showing "None selected"
- A green "Register" button
- A link for "Back Home" below the Register button

By clicking the **Register** button, you will receive a confirmation email in the inbox of the email address provided during the DECISO Digital Ecosystem account registration.

 If you want to delete your account, click on the link in the confirmation email.

 If you don't want to create your account, you can access the DECISO Digital Ecosystem to:

- display the events list;
- display the events pages;
- register for events.

About editing account information, please go to page 36.

Login

If you have a DECISO Ecosystem account, go to the login page by clicking on the menu link **Login**.

Enter your email address and password in the available fields and click the **Log in** button.

Homepage

Once you have completed the login, you will be automatically re-directed to the DECISO Digital Ecosystem homepage.

The homepage displays the DECISO Digital Ecosystem events list.

The list is pre-ordered by the START DATE and pre-filtered by the ALL options.

On the right side, by selecting the **EVENT STATUS** options, you can filter the list by UPCOMING, RUNNING or ENDED status, and by selecting the **ORDER BY** options, you can order the list by LAST CONTRIBUTION, A-Z or Z-A.

Instead, to display the MY EVENTS or the JOINED EVENTS lists, click on the **FILTERS** links at the top.

The **LOAD MORE** button allows you to display more events on the page.

On this page, you can:

- join/disjoin an event;
- embed an event;
- delete an event;
- add an event;
- display an event page.

If you want to join an event, click the **+** button on its preview. Instead, to disjoin an event, click the **✓** button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

 The event administrator can't join/disjoin his event.

If you want to embed an event, click the button on its preview. Then, embed the code generated to share event content on your website.

If you want to delete an event, click the button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button. A notification email will be sent to joined and registered users and also to you.

 The event administrator only can delete the event.

About adding and displaying an event, please go to page 12 and page 13.

Add event

If you want to add an event, click the **Add event** button on the right side.

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "ADD EVENT" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form contains the following fields and options:

- Title (*)
- Description (*)
- Organiser
- Event dates (*)
- Timezone (*) Select an item ▾
- Event type (*) Select an item ▾
- Project None selected ▾
- Pilot (*) Select an item ▾
- Event location (*) On web Live event
- Notes
- Save changes button

The modal requires you to fill in all the following mandatory fields:

- title;
- description;
- event dates;
- timezone;
- event type;
- pilot;
- event location.

Then, click the **Save changes** button to add the event to the list.

 Only DECISO project events will also appear on the website NEWS & EVENTS page.

About event and event content management, please go to the following pages.

Event page

If you want to display detailed information about an event, click on its preview in the list, and the event page will appear in a new tab.

On this page, you can:

- join/disjoin the event;
- delete the event;
- invite users to join the event;
- edit the event;
- send an email to joined users;
- change the event picture;
- upload the information sheet for the event registration;
- open/close the event registration;
- view registration list;
- register for the event;
- manage event content (e.g. agenda, post, document, video, gallery, meeting).

If you want to join the event, click the **+** button on the right side. Instead, to disjoin the event, click the **✓** button on the right side. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

 The event administrator can't join/disjoin his event.

If you want to delete the event, click the button on the right side. Then, click the **Confirm** button. A notification email will be sent to joined and registered users and also to you.

 The event administrator only can delete the event.

If you want to invite users to join the event, click the button on the right side.

Then, search for users not already added among the DECISO Digital Ecosystem users.

Once you have found the user you are looking for, click the **ADD** button to add the user to the joined users list. The newly added user will receive a notification email in the inbox of the email address provided during the DECISO Digital Ecosystem account registration.

You can remove users already added by clicking the corresponding button.

Once you have finished adding, click the **Close** button.

You can also display joined users by clicking on the corresponding link among the detailed information about the event.

 The event administrator only can invite users to join the event.

 Added users can disjoin the event using the procedure explained on the previous pages.

About editing an event, please go to page 23.

If you want to send an email to joined users, click the button on the right side.

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "SEND EMAIL TO JOINED USERS" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. Inside the modal, there is a user profile indicator for "CNR" with a small 'x' icon next to it. Below this, there is a checkbox labeled "Send to registered users, too". Underneath the checkbox are three input fields: "Insert a valid e-mail address and press Enter", "Subject", and "Body". At the bottom center of the modal is a green "Send email" button.

Then, after entering the Subject, the Body, and possible additional email addresses, click the **Send email** button. Joined users will receive a notification email in the inbox of the email address provided during the DECISO Digital Ecosystem account registration. You can remove default users by clicking the corresponding **X** button.

You can also send the email to registered users by checking the box in the modal.

 The event administrator and joined users only can send emails. If the sender is a joined user, the event administrator will also receive a notification email.

If you want to change the event picture, click on it.

Then, upload your photo and click the **Save** button.

- The new picture will overwrite the old/default one.
- The event administrator only can change the event picture.

If you want to upload the information sheet for the event registration, click the **Upload file** button in the information sheet console.

Then, for events related to the DECISO project, the modal requires you to fill in all fields to generate the default DECISO event information sheet.

A screenshot of a modal window titled "DEFAULT FILE FIELDS". It contains four input fields with placeholder text: "Link to additional info (Please insert a URL)", "Name of the person responsible for the workshop/event (Please insert first name and last name)", "Name of the person responsible for data processing (Please insert first name and last name)", and "Email of the person responsible for data processing (Please insert a contact e-mail)". An "Upload" button is located at the bottom right.

Instead, for events related to other projects, the modal requires you to upload the custom event information sheet.

A screenshot of a modal window titled "UPLOAD EVENT INFORMATION SHEET". It features a large dashed orange box in the center with the text "Drop file here or click to upload". An "Upload" button is located at the bottom right.

The ⓘ button allows you to display the *Information sheet guideline*.

By clicking the **Upload** button, the information sheet will be saved.

Click on the **Download information sheet** link to download the last updated file.

 By saving a new file, the old one, if any, will be overwritten.

If you want to open the event registration, click the **Open registration** button in the event registration control console.

 Without any information sheet, open registration isn't possible.

If you want to close the event registration, click the **Close registration** button in the event registration control console.

If you want to display and download the Excel file of the registered people list, click the **View registered people** button in the event registration control console.

 The event administrator only can display and manage the information sheet console and the event registration control console.

About event registration and event content management, please go to page 19 and page 24.

Event registration

If you want to register for an event, click the **Register** button on the right side of the event page.

If you do not have a DECISO Digital Ecosystem account, in the first part of the event registration, the mandatory fields are:

- email;
- confirm email;
- first name;
- last name;
- country;
- type of stakeholder
- user type.

REGISTRATION FOR 5° CONFERENZA NAZIONALE SULL'ECONOMIA CIRCOLARE ×

E-mail (*)

Confirm e-mail (*)

I accept and confirm the [event information sheet and consent form \(*\)](#)

First name (*)

Last name (*)

Country (*)

Type of stakeholder (*)

Notes

Simple user Organization user

Confirm my presence at the event

In the second part, the event registration modal requires some additional specific fields depending on the user type.

In particular, for the **Simple user**, the mandatory fields are gender and profile.

The form for a Simple user includes the following fields and options:

- Gender (*) **Select an item** (dropdown menu)
- Profile (*) **None selected** (dropdown menu)
- Company/Organization (text input field)
- Company/Organization type **None selected** (dropdown menu)
- Website (text input field)
- Phone (text input field)
- I want to be part of the DECISO Ecosystem
- Confirm my presence at the event** (button)

Instead, for **Organization user** the mandatory fields are company/organization, company/organization type and website.

The form for an Organization user includes the following fields and options:

- Gender **Select an item** (dropdown menu)
- Profile **None selected** (dropdown menu)
- Company/Organization (*) (text input field)
- Company/Organization type (*) **None selected** (dropdown menu)
- Website (*) (text input field)
- Phone (text input field)
- I want to be part of the DECISO Ecosystem
- Confirm my presence at the event** (button)

Don't forget to read the *event information sheet and consent form*, then tick the corresponding box and click the **Confirm my presence at the event** button. You will receive a confirmation email in the inbox of the email address provided during the event registration.

 If you want to delete this subscription from the event, click on the link in the confirmation email.

During event registration, you can also register a DECISO Digital Ecosystem account by ticking all the boxes and entering your password and confirm password.

The screenshot shows a registration form with the following elements:

- I want to be part of the DECISO Ecosystem
- The information you are sharing will be used for event and platform registration.
- I accept and confirm the [terms and conditions](#) (*)
- Password (*)
- Confirm password (*)
-

By clicking the **Confirm my presence at the event** button, you will receive a confirmation email in the inbox of the email address provided during the event registration.

 If you want to delete your account, click on the link in the confirmation email.

If you have a DECISO Ecosystem account, after logging in, click the **Register** button on the right side of the event page.

The modal, prefilled in with the account personal information, requires you only to fill in the mandatory field type of stakeholder.

REGISTRATION FOR 5° CONFERENZA NAZIONALE SULL'ECONOMIA CIRCOLARE ×

The information you are sharing will be used for event registration only.

E-mail (*)

I accept and confirm the [event information sheet and consent form](#) (*)

First name (*)

Last name (*)

Country (*)

Simple user Organization user

Gender

Profile

Company/Organization (*)

Company/Organization type (*)

Website (*)

Phone

Type of stakeholder (*)

Notes

Confirm my presence at the event

Don't forget to read the *event information sheet and consent form*, then tick the corresponding box and click the **Confirm my presence at the event** button. You will receive a confirmation email in the inbox of the email address provided during the DECISO Digital Ecosystem account registration.

 If you want to delete this subscription from the event, click the **Registered** button on the right side of the event page.

Edit event

If you want to edit an event, click the button on the right side of the event page.

EDIT EVENT

Title (*)
5° Conferenza Nazionale sull'economia circolare

Description (*)
La Conferenza Nazionale sull'economia circolare giunge quest'anno alla quinta edizione e si svolgerà il 16 maggio a Roma per presentare il Rapporto sull'economia circolare 2022, elaborato dal Circular Economy Network in collaborazione con ENFA e

Organiser
Cen-Enea con il patrocinio del Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica e della

Event dates (*)
05/16/2024 10:00 - 05/16/2024 16:00

Timezone (*) (GMT+01:00) Amsterdam, Berlin, Bern, Rome, Stockholm, Vienna ↕

Event type (*) OTHER EVENT ↕

Project None selected ↕

Pilot (*) No pilot ↕

Event location: On web Live event

Current event address Via Palermo 00184 Italy Change

Notes
La 5° Conferenza nazionale sull'economia circolare si svolgerà il 16 maggio a Roma, presso il Naz

Save changes

Then, after editing, click the **Save changes** button to save changes.

 The event administrator only can edit the event.

Event content management

If you want to add content to an event, go to the panel on the left side of the event page.

On this panel, you can:

- add the agenda;
- add a post;
- add a document;
- add a video;
- add a gallery;
- start a video conference.

If you want to add the agenda, click the **Add agenda** button on the panel.

 A screenshot of a form for adding an agenda item. On the left is a file upload area with a dashed border and text: "Drag Your Files Here Or", "Scegli file", "Seleziona file", and "We accept the following extensions: pdf, doc, docx, xls, xlsx, ppt, pptx, txt, jpeg, png, gif, svg". On the right, there are two input fields: "Insert a title" and "Insert a description". Below the description field is a "SUBMIT" button.

Then, after uploading your file and filling in all the required fields, click the **SUBMIT** button to add the agenda to the event page.

 button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

 The event administrator only can add and delete the agenda.

If you want to add a post, click the **Add post** button on the panel.

Then, after writing something, click the **POST** button to add the post to the event page.

 The event administrator and joined users only can add posts.

 button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

 button to save changes.

 The post author only can edit and delete the post, except for the event administrator.

If you want to add a document, click the **Add document** button on the panel.

Then, after uploading your file and filling in all the required fields, click the **SUBMIT** button to add the document to the event page.

 The event administrator and joined users only can add documents.

 button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

 button to save changes.

 Users can edit and delete only their own uploaded documents, except for the event administrator.

If you want to add a video, click the **Add video** button on the panel.

Then, after filling in all the required fields, click the **SAVE** button to add the video to the event page.

 The event administrator and joined users only can add videos.

🔔 If you want to delete the video, click the 🗑️ button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

🔔 If you want to edit the video, click the ✎ button on its preview. Then, after editing, click the 📁 button to save changes.

🔔 Users can edit and delete only their own uploaded videos, except for the event administrator.

If you want to add a gallery, click the **Add gallery** button on the panel.

Then, after uploading your files and filling in all the required fields, click the **SUBMIT** button to add the gallery to the event page.

🔔 The event administrator and joined users only can add galleries.

🔔 If you want to delete the gallery, click the 🗑️ button on its preview. Then, click the **Confirm** button.

🔔 If you want to delete an image, click the 🗑️ button on its preview.

🔔 If you want to edit the gallery, click the ✎ button on its preview. Then, after editing, click the 📁 button to save changes.

 If you want to add other images to the gallery, click the **+** button on the gallery preview. Then, after uploading your files, click the **Submit** button to update the gallery.

 Users can edit and delete only their own uploaded galleries, except for the event administrator.

If you want to start a video conference, click the **Start video conference** button on the panel.

START VIDEO CONFERENCE ×

Name (*)
Insert a name

Meeting Dates (*)

Timezone (*) Select an item ▾

Do you want event's joined and registered users to be informed about the meeting creation?

OK

Then, after filling in all the required fields, click the **OK** button to add the video conference details to the event page and display the Jitsi meeting page in a new tab.

 The event administrator and joined users only can start video conferences.

 button on its preview.

 The video conference creator only can delete the video conference, except for the event administrator.

 Because the event administrator and joined users only can display video conference details on the event page, you can also send a notification email, with the Jitsi meeting link, to registered users by checking the box in the start video conference modal.

 You can open the agenda and documents in a new tab, unlike the images that remain the same, by clicking on their previews.

 button on its preview. A notification email will be sent to the event administrator.

 Like button.

 Write a comment button.

News section

If you want to go to the news section, click the **News** button on the top menu.

The news section displays the DECISO Digital Ecosystem news list.

The list is pre-ordered by the DATE.

The **LOAD MORE** button allows you to display more news on the page.

On this page, you can:

- delete a news;
- add a news;
- display a news page.

If you want to delete a news, click the button on its preview.

 The creator only can delete the news.

About adding and displaying a news, please go to page 31 and page 32.

Add news

If you want to add a news, click the **Add news** button on the right side.

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "ADD NEWS" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form contains the following fields:

- Title (*)
- Subtitle
- A mandatory instruction: "YOU HAVE TO FILL TEXT FIELD OR LINK FIELD TO ADD A NEWS (*)"
- Text (with a large text area)
- Link (with a large text area)
- Projects (with a dropdown menu showing "None selected")
- A "Save changes" button at the bottom right.

The modal requires you to fill in all the following mandatory fields:

- title;
- text or link.

Then, click the **Save changes** button to add the news to the list.

 Only DECISO project news will also appear on the website NEWS & EVENTS page.

News page

If you want to display detailed information about a news, click on its preview in the list, and the news page will appear in a new tab.

On this page, you can:

- delete the news;
- edit the news;
- change the news picture.

If you want to delete the news, click the button on the right side.

 The creator only can delete the news.

About editing a news, please go to page 34.

If you want to change the news picture, click on it.

Then, upload your photo and click the **Save** button.

- The new picture will overwrite the old/default one.
- The creator only can change the news picture.

Edit news

If you want to edit a news, click the button on the right side of the news page.

EDIT NEWS X

Title (*)
Title

Subtitle
Subtitle

YOU HAVE TO FILL TEXT FIELD OR LINK FIELD TO ADD A NEWS (*)

Text

www.link.com

Projects **DECISO** ▾

Save changes

Then, after editing, click the **Save changes** button to save changes.

 The creator only can edit the news.

Password recovery

If you forgot your password, click on the menu link **Login** to recover your password.

The screenshot shows a 'LOGIN' form with a close button (X) in the top right corner. It contains two input fields: 'E-mail' with a placeholder 'Username' and 'Password' with a placeholder 'Password' and a visibility toggle icon. Below the fields are three buttons: a green 'Log in' button, a green 'Forgot password?' link, and a grey 'Need to register?' link.

Then, click on the **Forgot password** link to enter your email address.

The screenshot shows a form for password recovery. It features a grey input field with the placeholder 'Insert your email', a green 'Submit' button, and a grey 'Back to login' link.

By clicking the **Submit** button, we will send you a recovery email with a link to reset your password.

Profile page

Once you have created a DECISO Digital Ecosystem account, after logging in, click on the link **Welcome ...** (1) on the right side to display your profile page.

On the profile page, you can display your account information.

On this page, you can also:

- edit your account information;
- change your profile picture;
- change your password.

If you want to edit the account information on the left side and the description, click the corresponding button to save changes.

If you want to edit the company/organization type and the profile, click the corresponding buttons to delete items.

If you want to change your profile picture, click on it.

Then, upload your photo and click the **Save** button.

 The new picture will overwrite the old/default one.

If you want to change your password, click the **Change password** button.

A screenshot of a password change form. The form has a white background and a thin blue border. It contains three input fields, each with a light gray rounded rectangular placeholder. The labels for the fields are "Your current password", "New password", and "Retype new password", all in a small, gray font. At the bottom center of the form is a green rounded rectangular button with the text "Save changes" in white.

Then, after filling in all the required fields, click the **Save changes** button to change your password.

DECISO Project Participants

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

KoYS Lab

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon research and innovation program HORIZON-CL6-2022 under Grant Agreement No 101082232